

SQUARE

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• What is Square and its Offerings ?

Since Square was first opened our doors in 2009, the world of commerce has evolved immensely – and so has Square. After enabling anyone to take a payment and never miss a sale, it saw sellers stymied by disparate, outmoded products and tools that wouldn't work together. So Square expanded into software and started building integrated, omnichannel solutions – to help sellers sell online, manage inventory, run a busy kitchen, book appointments, engage loyal buyers, and hire and pay staff. And across it all, it has embedded financial services tools at the point of sale, so merchants can access a business loan and manage their cash flow all in one place.

<https://squareup.com/us/en>

Details

Industries

FinTech Hardware Mobile Payments

Retail Technology

Headquarters Regions

San Francisco Bay Area, West Coast, Western US

Founded Date

Feb 1, 2009

Founders

Buzz Andersen, Jack Dorsey, Jim McKelvey

Operating Status

Active

Last Funding Type

Post-IPO Equity

Also Known As

Block

Legal Name

Block, Inc.

- **Founding Date**

2009

- **Employee Size**

8521 (as of 2021)

- **Location**

San Fransisco , California , United States

- **Funding History**

Stock Symbol NYSE:SQ	Lead Investments 3
Investments 21	Exits 4
Funding Rounds 10	Total Funding Amount \$601.2M

- The top shareholders of Block are Jack Dorsey, Morgan Stanley, Vanguard Group, BlackRock, T. Rowe Price.
- Jack Dorsey, the company's CEO, owns 12.7%.
- The top five institutional investors own roughly 34% of the company.

1. Jack Dorsey

Jack Dorsey owns 50.8 million shares of Block, representing 12.7% of total shares outstanding

2. Morgan Stanley

Morgan Stanley owns 27 million shares of Block, representing 6.8% of total shares outstanding.

3. Vanguard Group Inc.

Vanguard Group owns 25 million shares of Block representing 6.3% of total shares outstanding

4. T. Rowe Price

T. Rowe Price owns 13.7 million Block shares, giving it a 3.4% stake in the company. The investment firm has \$1.69 trillion in AUM

5. Jennison Associates

Jennison Associates owns roughly 3.4% of the company, or 13.6 million shares.

- **Total Addressable Market (TAM)**

In an investor presentation last December, Square's management outlined a [total addressable market](#) (TAM) of \$100 billion for its Seller ecosystem and \$60 billion for Cash App.

Seller ecosystem represents a \$85B+ opportunity in the U.S.

Cash App ecosystem has a large opportunity in consumer financial services: \$9 trillion in addressable volume in the U.S. alone

Significant opportunities in serving larger sellers

Cash App ecosystem represents a \$60B+ revenue opportunity in the U.S.

- **Sales Addressable Market (SAM)**

- **Strategies to Expand Addressable Market**

Opportunity to expand on strong growth with digital natives

~260M Potential Customers

	U.S. Population	Age	Mean Income	Cash App % of Monthly Actives	Cash App % of Inflows
Generation Z	~56M	13 – 25	\$39K	34%	27%
Millennials	~72M	26 – 41	\$85K	38%	44%
Generation X	~67M	42 – 57	\$113K	20%	22%
Baby Boomers	~66M	58 – 76	\$79K	8%	7%

Sources: 2017 U.S. Census, U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics. Cash App inflows for the 12 months ending 3/31/21, and Cash App monthly actives as of March 2021. Does not include actives or inflows from actives who have not gone through the identity verification process with Cash App. Income data from U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics 2020 Consumer Expenditure Survey.

Multiple strategies to expand our addressable market

Circles are illustrative of opportunities to expand addressable market, but are not proportional or to scale.

• **Value Proposition**

Square offers seven primary value propositions: accessibility, price, convenience, customization, performance, risk reduction, and brand/status.

• **Unique Offering**

- 1.** Unlike loans from commercial banks, merchant cash advances through Square Capital had no set time frames by which the loans must be repaid.
- 2.** Also With its two-sided network, Square has data from the businesses, as well as the consumers, which is a dynamic that arguably no other company has. This is extremely valuable and provides a competitive advantage because it gives Square massive optionality.
- 3.** Square allows them to connect their existing service applications with its solution so they can sync price, item, and sales data.
- 4.** The company enables customization. Clients receive point-of-sale (POS) kits with guides that explain how to set up devices and software. The guides and kits are tailored by industry sub-sector (retail, food trucks, pop-up shops, salons/spas, bakeries/cafes, and bars/restaurants). Also, clients can use their Square data to develop custom apps.
- 5.** Square can deliver analysis of exactly how well the marketing works on new and returning customers. Thanks to its credit card readers, Square sees exactly how much money you spend after receiving a direct marketing message

• Type of Solution Offering

Payments ▾	Point of Sale ▾	Hardware ▾	More Tools ▾
Square Payments	Point of Sale Overview	Reader for Magstripe	Online Store
In Person	Square Point of Sale	Square Reader for contactless and chip	Online Checkout
By Invoice	Square for Restaurants	Terminal	Checking
On Your Computer	Square for Retail	Stand	Loans
On Your Website	Square Appointments	Register	Savings
Buy Now, Pay Later		Shop Hardware	Payroll
Risk Manager	Developers ▾	Rent Hardware	Team Management
Payment Platform	Developer Platform	Buy in Store	Marketing
Payments Security	Reader SDK	Compare Hardware	SMS Marketing
Transfers	In-App Payments SDK		Messages
Merchant Services	Online Payments APIs		Loyalty
	Documentation		Dashboard
	Developer Dashboard		Gift Cards
			Customer Directory
			Inventory Management
			Photo Studio
			Square KDS

• Pricing

Square Stand

A powerful iPad point of sale with an intuitive, customer-driven checkout and integrated payments — no readers required.

\$149 or \$14/mo over 12 months*

[Learn more →](#) [Buy](#)

Coming soon

Square Stand Mount

All the power of our signature iPad POS with the versatility to go anywhere in your store.

\$149 or \$14/mo over 12 months*

[Learn more →](#) [Notify me](#)

Square Register

Our most complete point-of-sale with two user-friendly displays, easy-to-use software options and built-in payments.

\$799 or \$39/mo over 24 months*

[Learn more →](#) [Buy](#)

Square Terminal

The all-in-one credit card terminal for payments and receipts.

\$299 or \$27/mo over 12 months*

[Learn more →](#) [Buy](#)

Square Reader for contactless and chip

A simple way to accept contactless cards, Apple Pay, and chip cards, at your counter or on the go.

\$49

[Learn more →](#) [Buy](#)

Square Reader for magstripe

Magnetic stripe reader for swiping credit cards anywhere on your smartphone or tablet.

First Reader FREE

[Learn more →](#) [Buy](#)

PRICING FOR API AND CARD BASED PAYMENTS -

<https://developer.squareup.com/docs/payments-pricing>

• Target Segment

In B2C business, the target customer segment for Square is broad. The financial unicorn decided to target the **individuals in developed countries who engage in financial transactions with other individuals** and this segment of population is large.

Square's initial target market might be small independent vendors, mom-and-pop ... market will include anyone who physically accepts payments in any form.

Retail →

All the retail tools you need—from open to close, in-store and online.

Food and beverage →

Tools for front of house, back of house, and everything in between.

Professional services →

Solutions for beauty, health, repair, and other professionals.

Large businesses

Build custom solutions with our scalable and secure platform.

Business Types ▾

Large businesses

Retail

CBD Retail

Coffee Shops

Quick Service

Full Service

Bars & Breweries

Beauty Professionals

Health & Fitness

Home & Repair Services

Professional Services

• Current Traction

How many merchants use Square?

2 million merchants

Last updated 11/26/17

How many users does Square have?

210 million buyer profiles

Last updated 1/1/21

Total number of Square active invoice sellers:

225,000

Last updated 5/5/17

61% of Square merchants process less than \$125,000 annually.

Percentage of all Square invoices that come from a mobile device:

nearly 50%

Last updated 5/3/17

Square seller industry breakdown by GPV:

- Food and Drink: 27%
- Retail: 19%
- Professional Services: 15%
- Beauty and Personal Care: 10%
- Healthcare and Fitness: 10%
- Home & Repair: 10%
- All others: 10%

([source](#), 12/31/20)

Number of businesses that have been given loans from Square Capital:

40,000 businesses

Last updated 5/3/17

Percentage of sellers that have been given loans from Square Capital that are women:

54%

Last updated 3/31/17

Percentage of sellers that have been given loans from Square Capital that are men:

46%

Last updated 3/31/17

Average size of a Square Capital loan:

\$6,000

Last updated 3/31/17

• Customer Acquisition Channel

Square's main channels are its direct sales team and its website. The company promotes its offerings through its social media pages, search engine marketing, display advertising, radio and TV advertising, print media, direct mail campaigns, and trade shows and events.

• Demographic Coverage

Square app is currently available in the **US, Canada, Australia, Japan, the United Kingdom, Republic of Ireland, France and Spain.**

But Square's hardware is only approved for use in the country for which it is intended. For example, hardware sold or intended for sale in the United States is not approved for use in Australia, Canada, Japan, Republic of Ireland, the United Kingdom or France.

